
Unlocking the Path to Reading Proficiency: Effectiveness of an 8-Week Reading Remediation Program on Grade 7 Students of Marilog High School of Agriculture

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Overview—This research investigated the effectiveness of an 8-week reading remediation program for Grade 7 students at Marilog High School of Agriculture during the 2020-2021 school year. The study aimed to enhance reading proficiency among students identified as Frustration Readers (FR) by the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI). The program employed targeted reading materials and weekly home visits for one-on-one guidance due to pandemic restrictions. Pre- and post-tests revealed that 69% of participants advanced to an instructional reading level, indicating significant improvement in reading comprehension. Results underscored the positive impact of sustained teacher support, customized interventions, and consistent monitoring on student literacy development.

Keywords—Reading Remediation, Frustration Readers, Reading Comprehension, Instructional Level

I. INTRODUCTION

Reading is undeniably one of the most important skills students should master throughout their academic life. It is also one of the keys that will bring them many opportunities. As educators, we have met different types of students with different reading abilities. Oftentimes, the students who are good readers are considered may not be the best students but they are one of the best in the classroom. Furthermore, reading is important for students to understand an array of materials such as textbooks, magazines, journals to make learning meaningful. These materials would help their writing, listening, and speaking skills better. These skills are essential throughout life. In addition, Ramelan(1990) states that reading is a good activity for learners; reading is also crucial and indispensable since the success of their study depends on the greater part on their ability to read. After conducting the yearly implementation of Phil-IRI, the language teachers found out that there are 13 of the Grade-7 students enrolled in Marilog High School of Agriculture School Year 2020-2021, are frustration readers (FR). That is why these identified students are closely observed and encouraged to be part of the 8-week remediation program that is required by the Phil-IRI to help students level up their reading skills. This 8-week remediation program is important in helping these students make their reading abilities better. As teach-

ers of these students, we have generalized that low scores and inability to participate in classes make sense. The ability to read words correctly and the ability to comprehend these words are connected. In our number of years of teaching, the students' comprehension problem is quite a problem.

a. Students' Background

Sixty-four percent (64%) of the students of the school belong to the Indigenous group and most of them are illiterate. It has been observed that these parents need assistance from someone whenever they need to fill in something. One of the factors that could affect students' skills in reading and comprehension is family. The home should be a pleasant place for students to read where parents help their children and encourage them to expose themselves to different reading materials. Another factor that we have seen in our students is their less exposure to reading materials. Reading materials are supposed to aid students in reading. Reading researches stress the importance of reading materials and practice in improving the students' reading comprehension skills. According to Liu and Kenzer (1987), as stated by Kartikasari (2017), reading materials are important as they influence the quality of learners and interests. Through this, the students will be encouraged to read. Moreover, as teachers, we have observed that teachers play an important role in encouraging students to read and correct whatever reading problems found in the classroom. However, due to the pandemic, teachers have less time to monitor the students. It becomes a challenge for the language teachers to keep track of the identified students who are categorized as frustration readers.

b. Teachers Background

The school factors in students' ability in reading; the curriculum, teaching method, and the teacher and student relationship are just a few. The curriculum. Marilog High School of Agriculture is one of the technical-Vocational high schools in Davao City. Currently, the school is under the K-12 curriculum. In addition to that, the school is participating in all DepEd required and Division required activities. One of the important activities that we have been actively participating in is the yearly Phil-IRI assessment. Phil-IRI required that all students enrolled in the current school year be assessed with their reading levels. The language teachers and the subject teachers are very supportive of this because the students' ability to read is one of the identified problems every year.

c. Teaching Method

Teachers play an important role in exposing students to different reading materials. We ask teachers to help us monitor frustrated readers and make them read different materials. After frustration and instructional level readers are identified, a copy of the summarized reading data is given to the different teachers. So, the teachers also allow students to read and encourage them to read for practice.

d. Teacher and Student relationship

One of our identified and effective strategies in monitoring students despite the pandemic is home visitation. Home visitation allows us to see our students in their homes. we would also be able to know what kind of learning environment they are in. So far, the remediation program is done through home visitation. We bring reading materials as well as learning materials and let students use them. The students can read different materials with the guidance of their teachers. In addition, our school administrator is very supportive to help our students level up their reading skills for this is one of the biggest factors in learning for life.

e. Objectives

This study aims to identify the effectiveness of the 8-week Reading Remediation Program based on the Phil-IRI. Specifically, it answers the following questions:

1. What is the reading level of the Grade 7 learners based on the Phil-IRI POST-TEST in S.Y. 2019-2020?
2. Who are the Grade 8 beneficiaries of the 8-week reading remediation program for S.Y. 2020-2021?
3. What is the reading level of the Grade 8 students for S.Y. 2020-2021 after the 8-week reading remediation program?
4. How effective is the 8-week reading remediation program in the improvement of the reading level of the students?

f. Scope and Limitations

This study specifically aims to determine the effectiveness of the 8-week reading remediation program for S.Y. 2020-2021. This study is limited to the selected Grade 8 students

who were still classified as Frustration Readers (FR) in the Phil-IRI Post-Test for Grade 7 learners of S.Y. 2019-2020.

II. METHODOLOGY

a. Methodological Framework

b. Data Collection

The flow of the 8-Week Reading Remediation Program

1. Determining the students who will undergo the 8-week reading remediation and intervention program (based on the results of the Phil-IRI POST-TEST for S.Y. 2019-2020).
2. Conducting the PRE-TEST to the identified beneficiaries of the 8-week reading remediation program.
3. Distributing the reading intervention materials (reading activities with short comprehension questions)
4. Recording of the learners' scores for 8 weeks
5. Monitoring of student beneficiaries through home visitations and virtual communications
6. Conducting the POST-TEST of the learners after the 8-week reading remediation program.
7. Analyzing the results of the students and determining whether there is an improvement in their reading comprehension skills.

c. Research Participants

The participants of the study are the Grade 8 learners in S.Y. 2020-2021 who are classified as Frustration Readers (FR) in the Phil-IRI Post-Test for S.Y. 2019-2020. These FR readers are the beneficiaries of the 8-week reading remediation program. They were given reading intervention materials for 8 weeks for them to have their self-paced reading exercises, assisted by their parents and/or guardians at home. The reading materials were distributed weekly together with the self-learning modules in their specific grade levels. Also, the reading intervention materials were intended for them to improve their reading comprehension skills. The table below shows the data on the reading profile of the Grade 7 students for S.Y. 2019-2020 based on the Phil-IRI POST-TEST. The results of the POST-TEST tell us that there are 40 (Male: 23, Female: 17) Grade 7 learners who are classified as Frustration Readers (FR). They are the target Grade 8 beneficiaries of the 8-week reading remediation program for the S.Y. 2020-2021.

d. Data Analysis

To determine the improvement of the reading comprehension skills of the students, the scores from the short activities in the 8-week reading remediation program shall be analyzed. Their pre-test and post-test scores shall also be analyzed and compared.

ENGLISH POSTTEST STAGE 2											
Total Number of Stage 2 Takers			Reading Level Profiles								Remarks
			Non-Reader		Frustration		Instructional		Independent		
M	F	TOTAL	M	F	M	F	M	F	M	F	
53	56	109	0	0	23	17	20	24	10	15	VALID
53	56	109	0	0	23	17	20	24	10	15	

TABLE 1: ENGLISH POST TEST STAGE 2

III. DEMOGRAPHICS

The respondents/beneficiaries of the eight-week reading program are the Grade 7 learners of S.Y. 2019-2020 who are classified as Frustration Readers (FR). They are living in Brgy. Datu Salumay, Marilog District, Davao City. Some of them live in the inner sitios of the barangay. Currently, the respondent/beneficiaries are in Grade 8 in the modular distance learning modality of the school.

IV. RESULTS OF ACTION RESEARCH

a. A. The Conduct of the 8-Week Reading Remediation Program

From the expected 40 Grade 8 participants of the reading remediation program, there were only 34 of them who enrolled for S.Y. 2020-2021 due to unavoidable circumstances during the pandemic. Other students have transferred to another school and others chose not to enroll for the current school year. As of July 26, 2020, due to the restrictions of the local government unit, the reading coordinators have reached out to only 13 out of 34 target beneficiaries because of the restrictions and quarantine measures of the local government unit. These 13 Grade 8 students were just living near the school and in Barangay Proper.

b. Results of the General Screening Test

The GST is a 20-item reading comprehension test. Those who scored 14 and above, they will no longer be undergoing the 8-week reading remediation program. However, for those who will score 13 and below, they shall be undergoing the remediation program. The GST is the first step in the Phil-IRI process. It also determines the current reading level of the students. The 13 students who were reached out by the reading coordinators were able to take the General Screening Test to determine and reverify their reading level. The results of the GST shall determine if the students are eligible to continue in the 8-week reading remediation program or not. The table below shows the GST scores of the 13 Grade 8 beneficiaries of the 8-week reading remediation program for S.Y. 2020-2021.

If the learners' GST score is 0-7, he/she must be given a passage that is 3 levels below his current grade level. If his/her score is 8-13, he/she must be given a passage that is 2 levels below his current grade level. The results mean that all the 13 Grade 8 students are eligible to continue the Phil-IRI process and shall be the beneficiaries of the 8-week reading remediation program.

c. Results of the Phil-IRI PRETEST

The 8-week reading remediation program commenced on August 3, 2020, and ended on September 28, 2020. Weekly home visitations were conducted to assist the students as they undergo the remediation program. On the first day of the program, a pretest was conducted to determine their current reading profile. During the pretest, the students shall read a passage according to their current reading level based on the results of the GST. They shall read orally the passage and the teacher shall listen and record the number of mispronunciations, omissions, substitutions, insertions, repetitions, transpositions, and reversals. After the oral reading, the students shall answer comprehension questions (multiple choice). The number of miscues during the oral reading and the results of the reading comprehension test shall determine the current reading profile of the students who are undergoing the remediation program. After successfully determining the current reading profile of the students, they were immediately given reading passages for their self-paced reading practice. These passages were taken from the Phil-IRI Passages from SET A to SET B. Some passages were taken from the internet. The reading coordinators focused on the following reading skills during their home visitation program:

1. Reading Comprehension Skills
2. Proper Pronunciation
3. Sight Words Practice Reading

d. Reading Remediation Proper

The table below shows the titles of the passages that the students shall be reading:

Names of Students (Grade 8 S.Y. 2020- 2021)	GST Scores (20 pts)	Current Reading Level Based on the GST Scores
Student 1	3	Grade 5
Student 2	6	Grade 5
Student 3	6	Grade 5
Student 4	8	Grade 6
Student 5	6	Grade 5
Student 6	3	Grade 5
Student 7	3	Grade 5
Student 8	8	Grade 6
Student 9	5	Grade 5
Student 10	5	Grade 5
Student 11	8	Grade 6
Student 12	6	Grade 5
Student 13	4	Grade 5

TABLE 2: GST SCORES

The table below shows the scores of the students from Week 1 to Week 8:

e. Results of the Phil-IRI POST-TEST for S.Y. 2020-2021

After the 8-week reading intervention program and weekly home visitation of the reading coordinators, a post-test was done.

The results of the Phil-IRI Post-Test show that 9 out of 13 (69 percent) beneficiaries of the 8-week reading remediation program improved their reading category from Frustration Readers (FR) to Instructional Readers (IR) in their identified reading levels. This means that with constant monitoring and weekly reading exercises, the reading comprehension skills of FR students shall improve until they reach their current reading level. However, for those who are still classified as Frustration Readers after the reading remediation program, they must be given more time for reading exercises and it is suggested that the intervention program shall continue.

V. REFLECTION

Reading is indeed an essential macro skill. It is a gateway to all the subject areas since everything in the teaching-learning process requires a learner to be a reader. Sad as it may seem, there are fresh graduates from the elementary level that are still having a hard time reading selected texts in their current grade level. They have to go down two levels for them to be able to start their reading practices. With this, the 8-week reading remediation program is a big help for those identified students amidst the pandemic because they were able to be provided with reading materials appropriate for their current reading levels. From their identified level, they were able to practice reading for a short period (8 weeks). This contributed to an increase in their reading skills based on the 10-item comprehension test every end of the home visitation sessions. The assistance and extra-mile efforts of the teachers paved the way for the improvement of their reading levels despite the pandemic. Although in the pre-pandemic days this is done in the comfort of the reading center of the school, the time was not wasted since the teachers were very eager to assist students by conducting home visitations and monitoring the students' reading practice at home. Therefore, the

Name	Grade Level (Based on GST Score)	Reading Profile (PRE-TEST)
Student 1	Grade 5	Frustration
Student 2	Grade 5	Frustration
Student 3	Grade 5	Frustration
Student 4	Grade 6	Frustration
Student 5	Grade 5	Frustration
Student 6	Grade 5	Frustration
Student 7	Grade 5	Frustration
Student 8	Grade 6	Frustration
Student 9	Grade 5	Frustration
Student 10	Grade 5	Frustration
Student 11	Grade 6	Frustration
Student 12	Grade 5	Frustration
Student 13	Grade 5	Frustration

TABLE 3: PHIL-IRI PRETEST

Passage 1	Grade 7 Literary Text (DepEd)
Passage 2 (Phil-IRI)	Frog's Lunch
Passage 3	Grade 7 Literary Text (DepEd)
Passage 4 (Phil-IRI)	Dark Chocolate
Passage 5	Grade 7 Literary Text (DepEd)
Passage 6 (Phil-IRI)	Pain
Passage 7	Grade 7 Literary Text (DepEd)
Passage 8 (Phil-IRI)	Pam's Cat

TABLE 4: TITLES OF PASSAGES

researchers would like to suggest that the reading remediation program shall be continued including the monitoring of

the progress of the students' reading levels, not just for the Grade 7 learners, but from Grade 7 to Grade 12.

	Aug. 10	Aug. 17	Aug. 24	Aug. 31	Sept. 7	Sept. 14	Sept. 21	Sept. 28
Passage No.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Total Items	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
Student 1	3	7	5	8	6	5	6	7
Student 2	8	8	9	8	7	8	8	9
Student 3	5	5	3		4	5	3	4
Student 4	6	7	7	8	7	9	8	9
Student 5	4	4	6	7	7	8	7	7
Student 6	7	6	7	8	7	7	8	7
Student 7	6	5	7				4	7

TABLE 5: WEEK 1 TO WEEK 8 SCORES

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Name	Grade Level (Based on GST Score)	Reading Profile (POST-TEST)
Student 1	Grade 5	Instructional
Student 2	Grade 5	Instructional
Student 3	Grade 5	Frustration
Student 4	Grade 6	Instructional
Student 5	Grade 5	Instructional
Student 6	Grade 5	Instructional
Student 7	Grade 5	Frustration
Student 8	Grade 6	Instructional
Student 9	Grade 5	Instructional
Student 10	Grade 5	Frustration
Student 11	Grade 6	Instructional
Student 12	Grade 5	Frustration
Student 13	Grade 5	Instructional

TABLE 6: READING INTERVENTION PROGRAM POST TEST